

Combinatorial Theorem for Multiple of Two with Exponents

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Abstract: Several combinatorial techniques are used in different ways for finding the formulae or binomial expansion for applications in computing science and other academic and research areas. This paper presents a theorem on the multiple of two with positive exponents.

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1. Introduction

Let us compare the traditional combination and optimized combination [2-6]. The optimized combination (binomial coefficient) is given below:

Traditional combination: $nC_r = \binom{n}{r} = \frac{n!}{r!(n-r)!}$, where $n, r \in N \cup \{0\}$ & $N = \{1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Optimized combination: $V_r^n = \frac{(r+1)(r+2)\dots(r+n)}{n!}$, ($n \geq 1, r \geq 0$ & $n, r \in N$).

Here, $V_r^{n-r} = nC_r = nC_{n-r}$ and $V_r^n = pC_r$, where $p = n + r$.

$$V_n^0 = V_0^n = nC_0 = nC_n = 1 \text{ \& } V_0^0 = 0C_0 = \frac{0!}{0!} = 1.$$

2. Combinatorial Theorem

The result of the below theorem is equal to multiple of 2 with exponents.

Theorem: $\sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = n2^{n-1}$.

Proof: This theorem is proved by examples with two consecutive positive integers. Let $n = 5, 6$.

$$\sum_{i=0}^5 i \times V_i^{5-i} = 5(2^{2-1}) \Rightarrow 0 \times V_0^5 + 1 \times V_1^4 + 2 \times V_2^3 + 3 \times V_3^2 + 4 \times V_4^1 + 5 \times V_5^0 = 5(2^4).$$

Then, $5 + 20 + 30 + 20 + 5 = 5 \times 32 \Rightarrow 80 = 80$. This is true for $n = 5$.

$$\text{Next, } \sum_{i=0}^6 i \times V_i^{5-i} = 6(2^5) \Rightarrow 1 \times V_1^5 + 2 \times V_2^4 + 3 \times V_3^3 + 4 \times V_4^2 + 5 \times V_5^1 + 6 = 6(2^5).$$

$6 + 30 + 60 + 60 + 30 + 6 = 6(32) \Rightarrow 192 = 192$. This is true for $n = 6$.

Similarly, we can prove this theorem for any positive integers less than or equal to n .

$$\text{Therefore, } \sum_{i=0}^n i \times V_i^{n-i} = n2^{n-1}. \text{ Note that } \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^{n-i} = 2^n.$$

3. Conclusion

In this article, we discussed the combinatorial technique including optimized combination (improved binomial coefficients) and also proved theorems with binomial expansion of coefficients that is equal to multiple of two with positive exponents. These combinatorial techniques will be of immediate interest to a broader readership of researchers in computational science and medicine [1].

References

- [1] Annamalai C (2010) “Application of Exponential Decay and Geometric Series in Effective Medicine”, *Advances in Bioscience and Biotechnology*, Vol. 1(1), pp 51-54. <https://doi.org/10.4236/abb.2010.11008>.
- [2] Annamalai C (2020) “Optimized Computing Technique for Combination in Combinatorics”, hal-0286583. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/9p4ek>.
- [3] Annamalai C (2020) “Novel Computing Technique in Combinatorics”, hal-02862222. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/m9re5>.
- [4] Annamalai C (2022) “Comparison between Optimized and Traditional Combinations of Combinatorics”, OSF Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/2qdyz>.
- [5] Annamalai C (2022) “Novel Binomial Series and its Summations”, Authorea Preprints. <https://doi.org/10.22541/au.164933885.53684288/v2>.
- [6] Annamalai C (2022) “Annamalai’s Binomial Identity and Theorem”, SSRN. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4097907>.